

Microbiological Quality and Food Safety Assessment of Vended Jollof Rice: Prevalence of Pathogenic Bacteria in Restaurants Serving Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka

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ARTICLE INFORMATION	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Published on 12th Dec 2025</p> <p>Keywords: Microbiology Food Safety Jollof Rice Prevalence Pathogenic Bacteria</p>	<p>Jollof rice, a culturally significant and widely consumed delicacy across West Africa, is a staple food frequently sold in restaurants and food outlets. Despite its popularity, little attention has been given to its microbiological safety. This study aimed to examine the microbial quality of Jollof Rice sold in selected restaurants in Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. A total of 4 samples were collected and analyzed using cultural and biochemical tests to identify food borne pathogens. The parameters assessed included total viable count, coliform count, and the presence of specific organisms such as <i>Escherichia coli</i> and <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>. The result revealed presence of coliform (<i>enterobacter</i> and <i>klebsiella</i> spp.) and <i>S. aureus</i>. Results revealed that while some samples (JF1 and JF3 from Nutrient Agar, JF1 and JF2 from Eosin Methylene Blue Agar and JF1, JF2 and JF4 from Mannitol Salt Agar) met acceptable microbiology standards ranging from no growth to 7.0×10^2 CFU/ml, others (JF4 and JF4 from MSA and EMB) exceeded the acceptable limits set by food safety guidelines (1.45×10^2 and 3.1×10^2) indicating poor handling and possible contamination. The presence of coliform and <i>S. aureus</i> in several sample suggests lapses in hygiene practices during preparation and storage. These findings suggest that Jollof rice served in restaurants may pose public health risks if proper food safety measures are not implemented. The study recommends enhanced hygiene training, stricter regulation and routine microbial testing to ensure food safety in restaurant settings.</p>

1. Introduction

While food is fundamental for human survival, improper handling and processing can transform it into a primary vector for the transmission of pathogenic microorganisms (Agu et al., 2013; Agu et al., 2014). Ready-to-eat (RTE) meals, particularly Jollof rice, hold significant cultural and dietary importance across West Africa, being widely patronized in restaurants, by street vendors, and at social gatherings (Anaukwu et al., 2015a; Anaukwu et al., 2015b). The nutrient-rich composition of Jollof rice—typically consisting of rice, tomatoes, vegetable oils, and accompanying protein sources like meat or fish—renders it highly susceptible to microbial proliferation if strict hygiene and storage conditions are not maintained (Agu et al., 2015; Awari et al., 2023).

The escalating prevalence of foodborne illnesses remains a critical global health concern. The World Health Organization (2020) reports that foodborne diseases impact millions of individuals annually, resulting in substantial morbidity and mortality, particularly in developing nations where food safety enforcement is often inadequate. Contaminated rice dishes have been frequently implicated in gastrointestinal infection outbreaks attributed to pathogens such as *Salmonella* spp., *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Bacillus cereus* (Obianom et al., 2023; Okoli et al., 2023).

Despite Jollof rice being a staple in Nigeria, the food service systems in many urban centers are plagued by challenges such as poor hygiene during preparation, cross-contamination, and prolonged storage at ambient temperatures (Agu et al., 2014; Agu et al., 2015). These factors create favorable environments for bacterial growth. Given that restaurant-prepared meals are consumed daily by students, workers, and families with limited regulatory monitoring, there are significant concerns regarding the public health risks associated with consuming potentially contaminated Jollof rice (Awari et al., 2023; Obianom et al., 2023).

This research is designed to provide empirical data on the microbial quality of Jollof rice served in commercial eateries. It aims to heighten awareness among food handlers and restaurant owners regarding the critical importance of food hygiene and proper storage protocols (Agu et al., 2013; Anaukwu et al., 2015a). Furthermore, the findings are intended to guide public health authorities in designing more effective strategies for monitoring food safety and preventing foodborne disease outbreaks (Agu et al., 2015; Anaukwu et al., 2015b, Okoli et al., 2023).

The primary aim of this study was to evaluate the bacteriological quality of Jollof rice sold in selected restaurants at Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, by isolating and identifying bacterial contaminants, determining their pathogenic potentials specifically biofilm formation and hemolytic activity and assessing the associated public health implications

2. Methodology

2.1 Research Design

This study employed an experimental research design focused on collecting and analyzing microbiological properties of Jollof rice samples sourced from selected restaurants within Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. The experimental design facilitated the detection, isolation, and identification of potential pathogenic bacteria. Such a design was selected because it provides accurate, measurable data regarding microbial presence and behavior (Cheesbrough, 2006).

2.2 Study Area

The research was conducted in Science Village, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Anambra State, Nigeria. The university has an approximate population of 5,000 students and staff who frequently purchase meals from campus restaurants and cafeterias. These establishments provide ready-to-eat meals such as Jollof rice, creating potential sites for foodborne pathogen exposure.

2.3 Sample Collection

A total of four Jollof rice samples were randomly purchased from different restaurants in Science Village, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. The samples were collected aseptically using sterile bags and transported to the Microbiology Laboratory for analysis. Handling of samples followed guidelines from the International Commission on Microbiological Specifications for Foods (ICMSF, 2002).

2.4 Sample Preparation

Each sample was homogenized in sterile nutrient broth. Serial dilutions were prepared to reduce microbial concentration to countable levels, ranging from 10^1 to 10^2 . One gram of Jollof rice (collected between 12:00–12:26 pm) was diluted in 10 ml of distilled water to form the stock solution. Sterile tubes containing 9 ml of nutrient broth were prepared, and 1 ml of stock was transferred sequentially through the dilution series using a sterile Pasteur pipette, mixing thoroughly at each step.

2.5 Culture Media and Isolation of Bacteria

Various culture media were used for selective and differential bacterial isolation: - Nutrient Agar (NA): general bacterial growth. - Eosin Methylene Blue (EMB) Agar: detection of *Escherichia coli* and other coliforms. - Mannitol Salt Agar (MSA): selective isolation of *Staphylococcus aureus*. - Biofilm medium: for biofilm-producing pathogenic microorganisms. - Blood Agar: observation of hemolytic activity. - Mueller Hinton Agar: antimicrobial susceptibility testing.

3.5.1 Pour Plating Technique One milliliter of the 10^2 dilution was inoculated onto sterile Petri dishes. Prepared media were poured into each plate, gently swirled to distribute uniformly, allowed to solidify, and then inverted. Plates were incubated at 37 °C for 24–48 hours depending on suspected organisms. Distinct colonies were sub-cultured to obtain pure cultures. Colony-forming units (CFU) were calculated using: $CFU = \text{number of colonies} / (V \times D)$.

2.6 Inoculation and Incubation of Isolates

A loopful of mixed culture was inoculated onto freshly prepared media under sterile conditions near a flame. Plates were inverted and incubated at 37 °C for 24–48 hours. Growth morphology, including form, color, elevation, size, and margin, was recorded.

2.7 Identification of Isolates

Bacterial isolates were identified using colonial morphology, Gram staining, and biochemical tests.

2.8 Gram Staining

A bacterial smear was prepared on a grease-free slide, air-dried, heat-fixed, and sequentially stained with crystal violet, iodine, ethanol, and safranin. Gram-positive bacteria appear purple, while Gram-negative bacteria appear red.

2.9 Biochemical Tests

Tests included sugar fermentation, urease, oxidase, methyl red, indole, motility, and Voges-Proskauer tests, following Ariyo and Obire (2021).

2.10 Catalase

Test A small amount of culture was mixed with 1% H₂O₂ on a slide; bubble formation indicated catalase positivity.

2.11 Citrate Utilization

Test Simmons citrate agar slants were inoculated with bacterial colonies and incubated at 37 °C for 24 hours. Blue coloration indicated positive citrate utilization.

2.12 VP/Methyl Red/Indole

Tests Peptone water (5 ml per tube) was inoculated and incubated at 37 °C for 24–48 hours. Methyl red indicated acid production (red positive, yellow/orange negative). Indole detection was done using Kovac's reagent (red ring positive). VP test used alpha-naphthol and KOH, with red indicating positive.

2.13 Motility Test

Semisolid nutrient agar tubes were stabbed with bacterial colonies. Diffuse growth indicated motility (positive), while growth along stab line indicated negative.

2.14 Urease Test

Urea-containing medium in bijou bottles was inoculated and incubated at 35 °C for 24–48 hours. Pink indicated positive urease activity; yellow indicated negative.

2.15 Sugar Fermentation Test

Peptone water with individual sugars and bromothymol blue indicator in test tubes with Durham tubes was inoculated and incubated at 35 °C for 24–48 hours. Acid production (yellow) and gas formation indicated positive fermentation, while green/blue indicated negative. Results were confirmed against Bergey's Manual of Determinative Bacteriology (Cheesbrough, 2006).

3. Data Analysis

Microbial counts were expressed as CFU/ml. Mean bacterial loads from different restaurants were compared and interpreted against ICMSF (2002) and WHO (2006) standards for ready-to-eat foods.

4. Results

The results of total viable counts, total coliform counts and total *staphylococcus* counts of the four Jollof rice samples (as shown in Tables 1, 2&3)

For Nutrient agar, samples JF1 and JF3 showed no growth, while samples JF2 and JF4 had few colonies (7.0×10^2 and 5.0×10^2 CFUml⁻¹) as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Total viable count on Nutrient Agar.

Sample Code	Dilution Plated	Raw Colony Count	TBC (CFU/ml)
JF1	10 ²	NG	Nil
JF2	10 ²	7 (TFTC)	7.0×10^2
JF3	10 ²	NG	Nil
JF4	10 ²	5 (TFTC)	5.0×10^2

Note: CFU/g calculated as Colony count \times dilution factor \div volume plated (1ml).

KEY: TFTC-Too few to count.

For Eosin Methylene Blue Agar, samples JF1, JF2 and JF3 had zero growth while sample JF4 had a total count of 1.45×10^4 CFUml⁻¹ as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Total Coliform Count on EMB

Sample Code	Dilution Plated	Raw Colony Count	Coliform Count (CFU/ml)
JF1	10 ²	NG	Nil
JF2	10 ²	NG	Nil
JF3	10 ²	NG	Nil
JF4	10 ²	145	1.45×10^2

On the other hand, sample JF4 on Mannitol Salt Agar had a total count of 3.1×10^2 CFUml⁻¹, JF3 had a total count of 2.0×10^2 while JF1 and JF2 showed no growth as shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Total Staph Count on MSA.

Sample Code	Dilution Plated	Raw Colony Count	Staph Count (CFU/ml)
JF1	10	NG	Nil
JF2	10	NG	Nil
JF3	10	2 (TFTC)	2.0×10^2
JF4	10	31	3.1×10^2

Only bacterial isolates on sample JF4 from EMB and MSA were subjected to cultural and biochemical test. The isolates were sub-cultured on EMB and NA and renamed as isolates A, B and C.

The result of the cultural and biochemical test of the isolates are shown in Table 4 and 5.

Table 4. Morphological and Biochemical identification of various bacterial isolates.

Isolate	Size	Colour	Texture	Elevation	Form	Margin	Gram	Glu	Lac	Suc	Mal	Fruc
A	Large	Red	Mucoid	Raised	Circular	Entire	-	+	+	+	+	+
B	Large	Pink	Mucoid	Raised	Circular	Entire	-	+	+	+	+	+
C	Medium	Yellow	Smooth	Convex	Circular	Entire	+	+	+	+	+	+

KEY: Glu-Glucose; Fruc-Fructose; Lac-Lactose; Suc-Sucrose; Mal-Maltose

Table 5: Biochemical Identification of Bacterial Isolates.

Isolate	Cit	Cat	Mot	Ure	Ind	MR	VP	Haemolysis	Biofilm	Identity
A	+	+	+	-	-	-	+	Gamma	-	<i>Enterobacter cloacae</i>
B	+	+	-	+	-	-	+	Gamma	+	<i>Klebsiella</i> spp.
C	-	+	-	+	-	+	+	Beta	+	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>

KEY: Cit-Citrate test; Ind-Indole test; Cat-Catalase test; MR-Methyl Red test; Mot-Motility test; VP-Voges-Proskauer; Ure-Urease test

The frequency of occurrence of bacterial isolates is shown in Table 6.

Table 6: Frequency of Occurrence of Bacterial Isolates

Bacterial species	Number of samples	Percentage frequency (%)
<i>Enterobacter cloacae</i>	2	50
<i>Klebsiella</i> spp	1	25
<i>Staphylococcus</i> spp	1	25

5. Discussion

The results of this study revealed that sample JF4 harboured the highest number of microbial loads as there were presence of microorganisms on the three media; Nutrient, Eosin Methylene Blue and Mannitol Salt Agar. The presence of coliforms in sample JF4 confirms water, soil contamination, possible fecal contamination or poor hygiene practices during preparation and serving. This is particularly concerning, as this organism is an indicator of environmental contamination and it is associated with urinary tract infections, respiratory infections particularly in immunocompromised individuals.

Also the presence of staphylococcus on JF4 from MSA is an indication of poor hygienic practices or poor handling. *Klebsiella* spp are opportunistic pathogens associated with gastrointestinal disturbances and other systemic infections, thus their presence in ready to eat foods poses a significant public health concern. These findings corroborate earlier studies by (Oranusi *et al* 2013) and (Chukwu *et al* 2018) who reported presence *Staphylococcus aureus* linked to poor storage and handling process.

On the other hand, the absence of microorganisms in JF1&JF2 from NA, JF1,JF2 and JF3 from EMB and JF1 and JF2 from MSA can be linked to effective sanitation and hygiene practices as well as good food handling and storage practices by the restaurant owners within science village in Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka.

6. Conclusion

The present study assessed the microbial quality of Jollof rice sold in selected restaurants within Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. Results revealed the presence of bacterial isolates in some samples. The bacterial isolates identified included *Enterobacter cloacae*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *klebsiella* spp. The presence of coliforms *Enterobacter* spp. indicates environmental contamination, while the detection of *klebsiella* spp. points to improper storage of rice after cooking. The presence of *Staphylococcus aureus* is an indication of poor hygienic practices or poor handling of the food. These findings confirm that jollof rice served within the university environment poses potential health risks to consumers if not properly handled and stored. The results also highlight lapses in food safety measures, personal hygiene of handlers, and sanitary practices in the restaurants studied.

7. Recommendations

Based on the outcome of this research, the following recommendations are made:

- Strict hygiene practices: Food handlers should maintain high standards of personal hygiene, including regular hand washing, use of gloves, and avoidance of direct hand contact with cooked food.
- Proper cooking and storage: Jollof rice should be cooked thoroughly and stored at safe temperatures. Leftover rice should not be kept at room temperature for extended periods.
- Safe water and utensils: Only potable water should be used for cooking, and all utensils, plates, and surfaces must be properly washed and disinfected before use to reduce cross-contamination.
- Food safety training: Restaurant workers within the university should undergo regular training on food hygiene and foodborne diseases, so they understand the health risks associated with poor handling practices.
- Routine monitoring and enforcement: The university management, in collaboration with health authorities, should conduct routine inspections of restaurants on campus to ensure compliance with food safety regulations.
- Public awareness: Students and staff should be sensitized on the risks of consuming improperly handled ready-to-eat meals and encouraged to patronize restaurants that comply with food safety standards.

- Further research: Additional studies should investigate the antibiotic resistance profiles of the isolates in more detail, since antimicrobial resistance is a growing global concern.

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